

In the present work all the non-associated liquids have been taken and the value determined. As will be seen, it comes to be 9.91. Substituting this value in *n*-hexane one obtains the value for H atom as 2.06 and C as 5.89.

While from ether the value for O comes to be 5.34. Similarly by substituting the values in different compounds, the following results have been obtained.

TABLE III

S. No.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
Atom	H	C	O	Cl	S	N	Double bond	Six-membered ring
Value	2.01	5.98	5.34	11.79	23.84	35.28	1.14	3.73

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DETECTION OF COBALT BY *o*-PHENYLENEDIAMINE

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o-Phenylenediamine has earlier been proposed as a reagent for the detection of nickel and vanadium. Nickel yields in presence of ammonia a bluish purple precipitate (Welcher, "Organic Analytical Reagents", Vol. II, p. 430; Feigl, *Oestr. Chem. Ztg.*, 1923, 28, 85; 1927, 30, 13; *Monatsh.*, 1927, 48, 445). But the test does not respond in dilute solutions, as the complex under these conditions is wholly dissociated into its constituents (Heiber *et al.*, *Z. anorg. allgem. Chem.*, 1929, 180, 89). *o*-Phenylenediamine hydrochloride develops an orange-yellow colour with a vanadate (Rosenthaler, *Mikrochem.*, 1937, 23, 194), but the test is not a sensitive one for vanadium. It has been observed that interaction of *o*-phenylenediamine with cobalt and dimethylglyoxime produces an intense unstable colour (Lee and Diehl, *Proc. Iowa Acad. Sci.*, 1950, 57, 187; *Chem. Abs.*, 1951, 7911) but no study of the interaction of cobalt and *o*-phenylenediamine, with particular reference to its applicability as a means of detecting cobalt, has been made. It has now been observed that *o*-phenylenediamine alone gives rise to an intense violet coloration with traces of cobalt in alkaline medium.

Qualitative detection of cobalt was carried out in aqueous medium. In aqueous medium the development of the violet colour is not immediate but requires a little time and shaking. Calcium, strontium, barium, magnesium, zinc, cadmium, lead, beryllium, aluminium, thallium, uranium, thorium, zirconium, titanium and bismuth do not interfere. Manganese interferes due to precipitation of higher manganese oxides in the alkaline medium. Ferric iron, silver, mercuric mercury etc. immediately oxidise the

reagent to an intense red colour, the metallic ions being reduced respectively to ferrous iron, metallic silver and mercury. Palladium develops a greenish blue precipitate or colour with violet fluorescence. Copper develops a violet unstable colour. But many of these interfering ions can be advantageously masked for the test. Of the anions, iodide, bromide, chloride, sulphate, acetate, nitrate, nitrite, borate, tungstate, vanadate, oxalate, phosphate, molybdate, fluoride, bromate and iodate do not interfere. Oxidising anions such as persulphate, dichromate, chromate, ferricyanide should not be present in more than trace quantities, as they oxidise the reagent immediately. Ions such as sulphite, ferrocyanide, when present even in small quantities, develop precipitates or colours with cobalt, and hence, should be absent. Thiosulphate or thiocyanate does not interfere when present in quantities usually encountered in qualitative detection. Citrate, tartrate, cyanide and ethylenediamine tetra-acetate mask cobalt and so they should be absent.

The exact nature of the coloured product, however, could not be established. The violet colour was extracted with *isoamyl* alcohol and the extract evaporated to dryness. The residue left showed positive test for cobalt. An aqueous hexammine cobaltic chloride solution, when treated with *o*-phenylenediamine solution and a trace of alkali and slightly warmed, immediately gives the violet colour. These qualitative tests indicate that the coloured product is an unstable cobaltic derivative.

A 0.2% aqueous solution (freshly prepared) of the reagent was used. Ammonia and sodium hydroxide may be used with equal advantage to make the medium alkaline; pyridine serves the purpose less readily. The violet colour is extractable with *isoamyl* alcohol. The visual sensitivity was found to be 0.1 γ Co in a concentration limit 1:10⁷ parts. The colour reaction appears to be more sensitive than rubenic acid (Rây, *Z. anal. Chem.*, 1929, 79, 94).

The reagent solution did not keep well and was always freshly prepared. The reaction being highly sensitive, it was found advantageous to work with 1 c.c. of a dilute solution containing 0.2 mg. of Co per c.c. and to compare the colour against blanks. The procedures for detection of cobalt in presence of different metallic ions are described below.

The reagent solution (1 c.c.) was added to the solution containing Co with Zn, Al, Be, Cd and Pb, followed by sufficient NH_4OH or NaOH to dissolve the precipitates of the hydroxides. A violet colour then developed on shaking.

When Ti, U, Th, and Zr were present, the violet colour appeared in the supernatant solution. Coloured product should be extracted with *isoamyl* alcohol in presence of enough NaOH when Cr is present. The effect of Fe^{III} could be masked by the addition of NaF to the solution, rendered just ammoniacal and the coloured product might be extracted with *isoamyl* alcohol. Similarly, the effect of Ag and Pd could be inhibited by the addition of pyridine (1-2 c.c.) and of Hg by excess KI before the addition of the reagent and ammonia.

In presence of Ni, 1 c.c. of the reagent was added followed by 2 c.c. of 1:2 NH_4OH to get a clear solution and after a few minutes' shaking, the colour was extracted with

isoamyl alcohol. The blank alcoholic layer (with nickel -*o*-phenylenediamine) is either colorless or pale bluish. The test must be carried out in the cold and an excess of the reagent should be avoided.

An exhaustive spectrophotometric study of the colour reaction was made. But the colour was found to be unstable and highly sensitive to p_H changes. The coloured product has two absorption maxima: $550m\mu$ and $750m\mu$.

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